

Comparative phylogenetics of the Asian genus "*Puntius*" and relatives (Cypriniformes; Cyprinidae): Explorations into the potential impacts of taxon and character sampling

Qiu Ren¹, Richard L. Mayden^{2,*}

¹Department of Integrated and Applied Sciences, Saint Louis University, 1008 S. Spring Ave. St. Louis, MO 63110, U.S. Email: qiuren815@gmail.com

²Department of Biology, Saint Louis University, 1008 S. Spring Ave. St. Louis, MO 63110, U.S.

*Corresponding author. Email: cypriniformes@gmail.com

Abstract

The southeast Asian genus "*Puntius*" has long been recognized as an artificial assemblage. Findings from a study by Pethiyagoda et al. identified *Puntius*, as currently recognized, as a polyphyletic group and consisting of five major lineages. Their study included only partial sequences of Cyt *b* and 16S and some morphological characters in a phylogenetic analysis that lead to the resurrection of genera and descriptions of new genera for species formerly in "*Puntius*". Given their use of partial sequences and few taxa from this diverse group, together with the taxonomic complexities across this group of fishes, the present investigation is an initial phase in the broad-scale analysis of the systematics of this complex. This diverse group offers excellent opportunities to examine the potential impacts of taxon and character sampling on the resolution, stability, and support for their phylogenetic relationships. In the present study, partial sequence data from the study referred to above was reanalyzed; this data set was then augmented with complete and/or partial sequences of an additional 22 species to compare with the previous findings. Results of the previous study were compared with analyses of complete and/or partial sequences and additional taxa. Pairwise topology tests were performed to examine congruence of topologies based on different sized data sets (taxa, characters). The results showed that interspecific relationships in the earlier study remained stable when the same length of data but additional taxa were added or the expanded data set was used. However, some relationships among clades were poorly resolved when using only partial Cyt *b* and 16s genes (i.e. relations of *Pethia*, *Dawkinsia* and *Haludaria* (= *Dravidia*)). Our results demonstrate that longer or more complete gene sequences, and increased taxon sampling, results in relationships that are more strongly supported and stable relative to those with fewer taxa and partial or short gene sequences.

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Introduction

Interests in the reconstruction or inference of genealogical relationships of elements of biodiversity in the post-Hennigian era have resulted in many investigations using both simulations with known priors and assumptions and standard analyses of species and/or populations (Wiley & Lieberman, 2011). With the emergence of less expensive and faster methods for sequencing genes for character data, there is great variation in the number and origins of genes and sizes of sequence reads in different studies (Briolay et al., 1998). The same applies to the number of taxa representing groups in analyses. Given this variation, questions

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remain if there are significant impacts on the results from varied analyses as to the impact of this variability on phylogenetic analyses in terms of numbers, robustness, and stability of a resulting tree(s). Some known impacts on resulting phylogenetic relationships with sequence data include the method of analysis, model(s) used, long-branch attraction (Felsenstein Effect), base composition at character sites for different genes, overall variability of genes used, use of nuclear or mitochondrial/plastid genes, number and variability of genes in a matrix, outgroup and ingroup taxa used, and character and taxon sampling (Wiley & Lieberman, 2011; Hillis, 1998). It should be noted that morphological data are not exempt from an array of similar and other issues that can impact the results of a phylogenetic analysis. With respect to character and taxon sampling, it has been shown through simulations and some analyses of data that having varying numbers of taxa and characters can have a serious influence on resulting phylogenies (Hillis, 1998; Hillis et al., 2003). Given that an important goal of systematics is to reveal historical relationships, phylogenetic analyses of specific groups often show "maturity" with respect to resolution, support, and consistency of relationships as more and more studies are conducted on a group or as additional taxa and/or characters are used for a group. This can vary depending on the taxa being examined and is a logical consequence of the scientific method wherein continued efforts are made to test previous hypotheses. Thus, maturation or stability of hypothesized genealogical relationships, using any type of data, is usually, but not always, accompanied with increasing information on the group via both characters and taxa used in an analysis. Excellent examples include a series of analyses of Cypriniformes species where increased taxon and character sampling has led to more stable and well resolved relationships of this hyper-diverse group of freshwater fishes (Chen et al., 2008; Chen & Mayden, 2009; Mayden & Chen, 2010; Mayden et al., 2007, 2008, 2009; Ren & Mayden, 2016; Stout et al., 2016; Schonhuth et al., 2018; Tan & Armbruster, 2018; Tang et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2013; Yang & Mayden, 2009; Yang et al., 2010, 2012, 2015).

Fish species of the order Cypriniformes, the most diverse clade of freshwater fishes (upwards to estimated 5,000 species) serve as an excellent group with which to investigate the impact of character and taxon sampling on phylogenetic resolution (Mayden et al., 2007; Mayden et al., 2008). Through the years the order has had uneven treatment of species relationships using morphological, allozyme, and sequencing data. Because of the sheer diversity of the group and underlying difficulties with morphological convergences in species, cypriniform species have traditionally been given minimal attention with regard to morphological and molecular systematics (Mayden et al., 2007). However, over the last two decades there has been a focused effort by many scientists in recovering species and supraspecific relationships (Chen & Mayden, 2009; Chen et al., 2008, 2009; Hirt et al., 2017; Mayden & Chen, 2010; Mayden et

al., 2007, 2008, 2009; Schonhuth et al., 2018; Stout et al., 2016; Tang et al., 2010; Yang et al., 2015).

As can be expected with initial phylogenetic findings for this poorly known group, earlier studies used single genes, usually mitochondrial, and small taxon sampling. Over the past twenty years, more information has been used in phylogenetic reconstructions in a number of studies of Cypriniformes. For various reasons, until only very recently phylogenetic reconstructions, a number of studies in the order examined only single or partial gene sequences and mostly data from the mitochondrial genome. More recently both mitochondrial and nuclear genes have been used, and one study with small taxon sampling used a phylogenomics approach (Stout et al., 2016). Thus, given the diversity of this order and the mixture of types of analyses and data, representative groups of the order serve as excellent opportunities for examining the impacts of taxon and character samplings. As evolutionary (phylogenetic) trees are fundamental to investigating comparative and evolutionary phenomena understanding the impacts of the above referenced variables is critically important.

The cypriniform genus "*Puntius*" serves as an excellent example to examine the impact of both taxon and character sampling on recovered phylogenetic relationships. This group has long been recognized as an artificial assemblage and "catch-all" genus that includes a large number of small and unrelated cyprinid species that are widely distributed in Asia (Myanmar, Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia, Cambodia, Sri Lanka, Nepal, India, Bangladesh and South China) (Kottelat & HeokHui, 2011; Kullander et al., 1999; Rainboth, 1996; Taki et al., 1978). There are roughly 280 valid species (Pethiyagoda et al., 2012; Froese & Pauly, 2018) in this complex, and while the complex as a whole is not monophyletic, there are monophyletic groups within *Puntius sensu lato* (*s.l.*). Most research on the "*Puntius*" complex has included species discovery and descriptions (Kullander & Fang, 2005; Kullander, 2008; Pethiyagoda et al., 2008), morphological research on limited endemic species (Pethiyagoda & Kottelat, 2005; Shantakumar & Vishwanath, 2006), and a few studies using molecular data (Fang et al., 2009; John et al., 2013; Moghaddam et al., 2013; Pethiyagoda et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2015). Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) used partial sequences of mitochondrial genes Cyt *b* and 16S (total ca.1000bp) and some morphological characters to investigate the phylogenetic relationship of 29 species in *Puntius s.l.* from India and Sri Lanka. Their analysis resulted in phylogenetic hypotheses from which the authors recognized three new genera, *Pethia*, *Haludaria* (Pethiyagoda, 2013) and *Dawkinsia*. Given the use of partial sequences and the few taxa in their study, together with the taxonomic issues surrounding the "*Puntius*" complex, hypotheses proposed by Pethiyagoda et al. provide a great opportunity for further investigation of both relationships within "*Puntius*" and impacts of taxon and character sampling.

The objectives of this study include the following. First, re-examine analyses of the partial sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. using partitioned

Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) approaches to see if analyses using different model strategies and algorithms reveal the same trees. Second, examine the impact of adding additional species, all with the same number of bp per gene, to the Pethiyagoda et al. data to see if analysis of incomplete sequences of this increased taxon dataset results in monophyly of some groups and sister group relationships consistent with those of the reduced taxon analysis of Pethiyagoda et al. Third, use the incomplete data set with the inclusion of complete sequences and additional taxa to examine relationships based on complete sequences compared to analyses above. Finally, a set of ML trees are reconstructed based on different lengths of data and pairwise topology tests are conducted to test congruence of topologies and examine the influence of data sampling on resulting phylogenetic tree(s).

Materials and methods

Taxon information

A total of 146 Cyt *b* and 16s sequences from 59 species (including outgroup taxa) were included in this study. The 77 sequences of 37 (ingroup and outgroup) species from Pethiyagoda et al. were obtained from GenBank. Remaining sequences were derived from other papers and/or from Genbank (see Table 1 for detailed taxon information). To limit the number of differing variables in this comparative analysis the selection of outgroup taxa was the same as those used by Pethiyagoda et al. Bayesian posterior probabilities and bootstrap values, representing support for nodes are abbreviated PP and BS, respectively.

Table 1. Information on taxa used in this study. Sources identified by * are from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012), those identified as ** are from Yang et al. (2010), those identified as *** are from Yang et al. (2015), those identified as # are from Yang et al. (2012), those identified as ## are from Arunachalam et al. (2012), and those identified as ### are from Saitoh et al. (2006).

16s	Cyt <i>b</i>	Species	Location	Country	Source
JF793573	JF793607	<i>Dawkinsia filamentosa</i>	Kottayam	India	*
JF793583	JF793617	<i>Dawkinsia singhala</i>	Menik River	Sri Lanka	*
JF793584	JF793618	<i>Dawkinsia srilankensis</i>	Pallegama	Sri Lanka	*
JF793572	JF793606	<i>Dravidia fasciata</i>	Chalakudy	India	*
JF793563	JF793597	<i>Pethia bandula</i>	Galapitamada	Sri Lanka	*
JF793590	JF793624	<i>Pethia conchoniis</i>	Aquar.spec.	N/A	*
EU604684	EU604676	<i>Pethia cumingii</i>	Bentota	Sri Lanka	*
EU604686	EU604678	<i>Pethia melanomaculata</i>	Kandalama	Sri Lanka	*
JF793578	JF793612	<i>Pethia nigrofasciata</i>	Mawanana	Sri Lanka	*
EU604682	EU604674	<i>Pethia reval</i>	KelaniRiver	Sri Lanka	*
EU604687	EU604679	<i>Pethia ticto</i>	Boncron	India	*
JF793564	JF793598	<i>Puntius bimaculatus</i>	Bentota	Sri Lanka	*
JF793565	JF793599	<i>Puntius cf. bimaculatus</i>	Minneriya	Sri Lanka	*
JF793587	JF793621	<i>Puntius cf. titteya</i>	Bentota	Sri Lanka	*
JF793567	JF793601	<i>Puntius chola</i>	Boncron	India	*
JF793569	JF793603	<i>Puntius dorsalis</i>	GinRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793571	JF793605	<i>Puntius dorsalis</i>	Mamallapuram	Sri Lanka	*

16s	Cyt b	Species	Location	Country	Source
JF793570	JF793604	<i>Puntius kelumi</i>	GinRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793568	JF793602	<i>Puntius layardi</i>	WalaweRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793577	JF793611	<i>Puntius mahecola</i>	Kottayam	India	*
JF793585	JF793619	<i>Puntius sophore</i>	Boncron	India	*
JF793566	JF793600	<i>Puntius thermalis</i>	Mawanana	Sri Lanka	*
JF793586	JF793620	<i>Puntius titteya</i>	KaluRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793575	JF793609	<i>Systemus martenstyni</i>	Pallegama	Sri Lanka	*
JF793579	JF793613	<i>Systemus pleurotaenia</i>	GinRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793582	JF793616	<i>Systemus sarana</i>	Boncron	India	*
JF793576	JF793610	<i>Systemus sp. 'Richmondi'</i>	Elahera	Sri Lanka	*
JF793581	JF793615	<i>Systemus spilurus</i>	Bentota	Sri Lanka	*
JF793580	JF793614	<i>Systemus timbiri</i>	MenikRiver	Sri Lanka	*
JF793558	JF793592	<i>Garra ceylonensis</i>	Homadola	Sri Lanka	*
JF793559	JF793593	<i>Garra mullya</i>	Chalakudy	India	*
JF793560	JF793594	<i>Labeo dussumieri</i>	Elahera	Sri Lanka	*
JF793561	JF793595	<i>Labeo dussumieri</i>	Alleppey	India	*
JF793562	JF793596	<i>Osteochilichthys nashii</i>	Chalakudy	India	*
JF793574	JF793608	<i>Gonoproktopterus jerdoni</i>	Srirangapatam	India	*
JF793591	JF793625	<i>Gonoproktopterus curmuca</i>	Chalakudy	India	*
JF793588	JF793622	<i>Tor khudree</i>	Mawanana	Sri Lanka	*
JF793589	JF793623	<i>Barbonymus schwanenfeldii</i>	Aquar. spec.	N/A	*
KP712668	KP712211	<i>Barbodes aurotaeniatus</i>	Vang vieng	Northern Laos	***
AY708216	EU241451	<i>Puntius bimaculatus</i>	N/A	N/A	Genbank
HM536772	HM536815	<i>Puntius brevis</i>	Siem Reap	Cambodia	**
KP712669	KP712212	<i>Puntius chola</i>	Kolkata	India	***
KP712683	KP712226	<i>Pethia conchoni</i>	West Bengal	India	***
DQ845880	AY004751	<i>Pethia conchoni</i>	N/A	N/A	Genbank
KP712635	KP712177	<i>Pethia cumingii</i>	N/A	N/A	***
KP712638	KP712180	<i>Sahyadria denisonii</i>	Aquarium		***
KP712684	KP712227	<i>Barbodes everetti</i>	Market	N/A	***
JX074090	JX074247	<i>Haludaria fasciatus</i>	Aquarium		#
N/A	KP659416	<i>Desmopuntius hexazona</i>	N/A	N/A	***
KP712636	KP712178	<i>Desmopuntius johorensis</i>	N/A	N/A	***
KP712670	KP712213	<i>Barbodes lateristriga</i>	Market	Thailand	***
HM536774	HM536817	<i>Puntius masyai</i>	Siem Reap	Cambodia	**
KP712631	KP712173	<i>Pethia narayani</i>	N/A	N/A	***
HM536778	HM536821	<i>Pethia nigrofasciatus</i>	Aquarium	N/A	***
HM536777	HM536820	<i>Oliotius oligolepis</i>	Aquarium	N/A	***
KP712671	KP712214	<i>Systemus orphoides</i>	Kampong Chhnang	Cambodia	***
KP712682	KP712225	<i>Pethia padamya</i>	Market	N/A	***
KP712640	KP712182	<i>Puntigrus partipentazona</i>	Aquarium	N/A	***
KP712639	KP712181	<i>Desmopuntius pentazona</i>	Aquarium	N/A	***
KP712608	KP659417	<i>Pethia phutunio</i>	N/A	N/A	***
KP712605	KP659413	<i>Barbodes rhombeus</i>	N/A	N/A	***
KP712604	KP659412	<i>Desmopuntius rhomboocellatus</i>	N/A	N/A	***
HM010702	HM010726	<i>Systemus sarana</i>	Bhavani sagar,Tamilnadu	India	##
KP712667	KP712210	<i>Systemus sarana</i>	West Bengal	India	***
KP712674	KP712217	<i>Systemus sarana</i>	Koshi Barrage	Nepal	***
AP011246	AP011246	<i>Puntius semifasciolatus</i>	Market	N/A	Genbank
GQ406260	FJ667463	<i>Puntius semifasciolatus</i>	N/A	N/A	Genbank
EU241452	DQ845880	<i>Pethia conchoni</i>	N/A	N/A	Genbank
KP712685	KP712228	<i>Pethia stoliczkanus</i>	Chaing Mai	Thailand	***

16s	Cyt <i>b</i>	Species	Location	Country	Source
KP712675	KP712218	<i>Puntius terio</i>	Kolkata	India	***
EU287909	EU287909	<i>Puntigrus tetrazona</i>	N/A	N/A	Genbank
AB238969	AB238969	<i>Pethia ticto</i>	Chang Rai	Thailand	###
HM536766	HM536809	<i>Puntius titteya</i>	Aquarium	N/A	**

Sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis

Nucleotide sequences were initially assembled using the program SeqMan 6.0 in the DNA Star package (DNASTar Inc., U.S.), with further manual correction. Sequences were aligned by Clustal W in MEGA 5 (Tamura et al., 2011) and translated into amino acids for confirmation of the alignment and assignment of codon positions, as well as detection of any stop codons.

Pethiyagoda et al. used Bayesian and Parsimony analyses. Herein, we employed partitioned ML and BI analyses. ML trees were constructed using RAxML v.7.0.4 (Stamatakis, 2006). The partition strategies by gene and codon were applied and GTRGAMMA model was applied in all analyses. A total of 100 distinct runs were performed using the default algorithm of the program. The tree with the maximum likelihood score was chosen as the best tree. Maximum likelihood bootstrap analysis (Felsenstein, 1985; Stamatakis et al., 2008) was conducted using RAxML using 500 replications. RAxML rapid bootstrapping algorithm and GTRGAMMA approximation were used in the analyses. Other parameters were set as default. Bayesian inferences were implemented using MrBayes 3.1.2 (Ronquist et al., 2012). The partition scheme and best-fitting model were selected according to Bayesian information criterion using PartitionFinder 1.0.1 (Lanfear et al., 2012). MrBayes analyses included 10,000,000 generations of Markov chains, sampling every 1000 generations to yield 10,000 trees. The first 25% of the trees were discarded as burn-in. A majority rule consensus tree was produced from the remaining 7,501 trees and was used to determine posterior probabilities (PP).

Topology comparisons

Four different data sets of Cyt *b* and 16s genes were created for the different comparative analyses. The first data set (Cyt *b*-P: 552bp) included the partial Cyt *b* sequences used by Pethiyagoda et al. and additional partial Cyt *b* sequences. The second data set (Cyt *b*-C: 1140bp) consisted of additional complete Cyt *b* sequences and the partial Cyt *b* data from Pethiyagoda et al. The third data set (Cyt *b*-P&16s-P: 1080bp) included additional partial Cyt *b* sequences together with partial 16S sequences and those from Pethiyagoda et al. The fourth data set (Cyt *b*-C&16s-P: 1700bp) was composed of additional complete Cyt *b* sequences and the partial 16s data set as well as partial Cyt *b* and 16S from Pethiyagoda et al.

In order to explore the influence of data sampling on the resulting phylogenetic relationships, tree topologies were determined from the best ML trees constructed using RAxML. The GTR+G+I model, chosen for topology comparison, was consistent with models used for constructing the best ML trees. All tests were implemented in Treefinder (Jobb, 2008) using the RELL (resample estimated log-likelihood) nonparametric bootstrap method with 50,000 replicates to generate null distributions. Only ML trees can be compared in using RELL and emphasis on statistical comparisons is limited to these trees. The null hypothesis tested was that all topologies are equally good at explaining the data.

Tree distance matrices were generated on four topologies to assess their pairwise similarities and differences using the symmetric distance of Robinsons and Foulds (Robinson & Foulds, 1981). Analyses were performed using Treedist in Phylip program (Felsenstein, 1993). Three paired-sites statistical tests, the Kishino-Hasegawa (KH; Kishino & Hasegawa, 1989), Approximately unbiased (AU; Shimodaira, 2002) and Shimodaira-Hasegawa (SH; Shimodaira & Hasegawa, 1999) were used to compare congruence of topologies under different sampling regime. All tests compared likelihood differences among tree topologies to the empirical variation in log likelihoods for a given data set.

Results

Re-examination of data from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012)

Analyses of the varied data sets (Cyt *b*-P: 552bp; Cyt *b*-C: 1140bp; Cyt *b*-P&16s-P: 1080bp; Cyt *b*-C&16s-P: 1700bp) resulting in differing topologies and the null hypothesis (H_0 : all topologies are equally good at explaining the data) was rejected ($P < 0.05$).

Bayesian reanalysis of data from Pethiyagoda et al. yielded a tree (Figure 1) consistent with that of Pethiyagoda et al. (Pethiyagoda et al. 2012; pp.74) but with notably lower nodal support. The ingroup formed five distinct clades as presented in Pethiyagoda et al. The supporting PP for these clades was lower in this analysis than those of Pethiyagoda et al. The PP for the *Dawkinsia* clade was 0.86(=86) in our BI tree but was 92 in Pethiyagoda et al.; the supporting PP for the relationships of *Pethia*, *Haludaria* and *Dawkinsia* was 0.53(=53) in Figure 1 while 71 in Pethiyagoda et al.

Relationships derived from the same data using ML (Figure 2, not collapsed), however, were different compared to those derived from BI and nodal support was notably lower for basal nodes. More specifically, the resulting ML tree was more resolved compared to BI tree, but had lower support for some clades, and the relationships of some clades were

different from those of BI tree. For example, the *Pethia* clade was basal within the ingroup of ML tree while it clustered with *Dawkinsia* and *Haludaria* in BI tree. However, topology testing revealed no significant difference between the ML and BI trees (KH: $P = 0.305$; AU: $P = 0.317$; SH: $P = 0.305$). However, the relationships of taxa within genera in both BI and ML trees were not exactly the same as those presented in Pethiyagoda et al.

Figure 1. Bayesian tree constructed using the data from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012).

Difference between analyses and trees with and without augmented taxa and data

The phylogenetic trees (BI and ML trees, Figures 1 & 2) constructed using data from Pethiyagoda et al. were compared with the phylogenetic trees (BI and ML trees, Figures 3 & S3) including additional taxa with the same sequence lengths (dataset: Cyt *b*-P&16s-P, 1080bp). These new, expanded trees (Figures 3 & S3) were partially congruent with Pethiyagoda et al. but only in that similar clades could be identified with varying levels of support. However, relationships among clades differed between analyses. Species of *Dawkinsia* formed a clade but this clade was not sister to *Pethia*. *Haludaria fasciata* formed a weakly supported clade with *Barbodes*, *Oliotius*, *Desmopuntius* and *Puntigrus*. Part of the *Puntius*

Figure 2. Maximum likelihood tree constructed using the data from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012)

Nodes with bootstrap lower than 50 were not shown.

sensu stricto (*s.s.*) clade formed a sister relationship with *Systemus*. *Puntius s.s.* was not resolved as monophyletic (Figures 3, 4, S1 to S4). *Puntius semifasciolatus* and other species were more closely related to outgroup taxa than to those of *Puntius s.l.* complex. Finally, with the addition of more taxa, eight clades were recognized in the increased taxon sampling data set while only five were resolved in Pethiyagoda et al.

When the data set of Pethiyagoda et al. was augmented with complete *Cyt b* (1140bp) and additional partial 16s (558bp) sequences of additional taxa (*Cyt b*-C&16s-P, 1698bp), the resulting trees (BI and ML,

improved resolution and higher nodal support compared to the tree resulting from the Cyt *b*-P&16s-P data set. Both trees revealed eight clades, compared to only five clades in Pethiyagoda et al., since more taxa were included, but clade composition differed from the later study; each clade represented a distinct genus identified by Pethiyagoda (2012) and Kottelat (2013). However, *Barbodes* did not form a monophyletic group. Furthermore, the relationships of *Desmopuntius*, *Puntigrus*, *Oliotus*, *Haludaria* and *Barbodes* and the *Haludria fasciata* clade were unresolved or unstable, respectively.

Table 2. Pairwise symmetric distances between topologies.

	Cyt <i>b</i> -P	Cyt <i>b</i> -C	Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P
Cyt <i>b</i> -P	—	114	116	108
Cyt <i>b</i> -C	114	—	122	120
Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	116	122	—	88
Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	108	120	88	—

Differences between trees derived from different lengths of data–topology comparisons

The ML trees using different sequence lengths are provided in S1 to S4. The results of the tree distance comparison (Table 2) showed the symmetric distance of Robinsons and Foulds ranged from 88 to 122. The shortest distance (88) in all pairwise comparisons was from Cyt *b*-P&16s-P vs. Cyt *b*-C&16s-P tree, and the largest distance (122) was the result of Cyt *b*-C vs. Cyt *b*-P &16s-P.

Table 3. Results of the KH, AU, SH tests. * indicates P -value less than 0.05.

Data	tree	KH (P-value)	AU (P-value)	SH (P-value)
Cyt <i>b</i> -P	Cyt <i>b</i> -P	—	—	—
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C	0.178	0.169	0.178
	Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	0.019*	0.016*	0.019*
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	0.028*	0.025*	0.028*
Cyt <i>b</i> -C	Cyt <i>b</i> -P	0.143	0.142	0.143
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C	—	—	—
	Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	0.018*	0.013*	0.018*
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	0.065	0.056	0.065
Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	Cyt <i>b</i> -P	0.046*	0.045*	0.046*
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C	0.039*	0.037*	0.039*
	Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	—	—	—
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	0.495	0.497	0.495
Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	Cyt <i>b</i> -P	0.013*	0*	0.013*
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C	0.099	0.092	0.099
	Cyt <i>b</i> -P&16s-P	0.328	0.327	0.328
	Cyt <i>b</i> -C&16s-P	—	—	—

Tree distance metrics cannot identify whether a greater distance is significantly larger than a lesser one (Felsenstein, 1993). In other words, tree distance comparison cannot provide information as to the statistical significance of differences. However, the KH, AU and SH tests can provide information as to significance of different log-likelihoods in pairwise topology comparisons. The results of topology comparisons are summarized in Table 3 and clearly demonstrate that there are differences

Figure 4. Bayesian tree constructed using the complete Cyt *b* and partial 16s (Cyt *b*-C&16s-P) data set, sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) was added "PT2012" at the end of taxon name in order to differentiate the newly added sequences.

in tree topologies depending upon the length of sequences and whether or not 16S was included in analyses. The partial Cyt *b* tree (S1) was not significantly different from results derived from the full compliment of sequences for Cyt *b* (S2) but did differ from partial or complete Cyt *b* when combined with 16S (S3 & S4). Results derived from the complete Cyt *b* sequence data set (S2), however, was only significantly different from partial Cyt *b* and partial 16S (S3), but not the complete Cyt *b* and 16S (S4).

Resulting trees (S3) from the dataset of partial sequences of both genes were significantly different only in comparisons to partial and complete Cyt *b* (S1 & S2), indicating significant signal in 16S even with partial data. The complete Cyt *b* and partial 16S data set (S4) was only significantly different from analyses of partial Cyt *b* (S1), again indicating strong signal in 16S.

Discussion

In general, data from multiple genes per species can be useful for resolving a species tree and greatly improve the resolution of a tree (Corl & Ellegren, 2013; Maddison & Knowles, 2006). This is in contrast to a single gene or partial gene sequence for taxa having a lesser possibility of reflecting the "actual" evolutionary relationships among species and strong nodal support.

In the present study, the same dataset of partial sequence data from two mitochondrial genes from Pethiyagoda et al. were reanalyzed using partitioned ML and BI approaches. In both instances resulting topologies were relatively congruent with that presented in Pethiyagoda et al. and each other but differed in some nodal support. This analysis suggests that partial Cyt *b* and 16s, together totaling around 1000bp, is indeed able, to some extent, provide phylogenetic information and resolve interspecific relationships. They are, however, not able to resolve the deeper nodes representing relationships among clades. For example, the PP support for the close relationship between *Pethia*, *Dawkinsia* and *Haludaria* was only 0.53 in Bayesian analysis (Figure 1) and was not resolved in ML analysis (Figure 2). Furthermore, the relationships of *Pethia*, *Dawkinsia* and *Haludaria* were not resolved from either the partial Cyt *b* & 16s data set (1080bp) or complete Cyt *b* & 16s data set (1780bp). This suggests that even 1780 bp of these genes is not enough to resolve relationships of deeper nodes. Resolution of relationships only occurred with increased taxon sampling and more complete sequences (Hillis, 1998; Mayden et al., 2008). Thus, it is highly recommended that studies, when possible, include as many taxa (both outgroup and ingroup) as possible and full lengths of multiple genes (mitochondrial and nuclear).

The results of pairwise symmetric distances between topologies indicated that the shortest distance (88) occurred between trees derived from the Cyt *b*-P&16s-P and Cyt *b*-C&16s-P data sets. These analyses also indicated that the results of KH, AU and SH tests detected no significant difference between Cyt *b*-P&16s-P and Cyt *b*-C&16s-P topologies. These results suggest that the trees derived from the two data sets above are consistent with one another. The largest distance (122) was between Cyt *b*-C and Cyt *b*-P & 16s-P trees which were significantly different; this indicates different topologies of the two trees and inconsistent phylogenetic patterns of relationships. The results of topology tests

suggest that the more similar the data sets are, the more congruent the phylogenetic trees are and vice versa. This study also indicates that a larger data set including multiple genes and more taxa is better able to provide a more resolved tree and stronger lineage support.

Support for continued use of minimal gene datasets

While the results above, based on one or two partially sequenced genes (in this case mtDNA genes), are mixed as to resolving relationships relative to using more complete sequences and additional taxa, analyses of single genes (ctDNA, mtDNA and/or nDNA) should remain acceptable and valuable for research funding and publication of results. Globally, various forms of biodiversity are disappearing rapidly and may have never been sampled, are rare, and, thus, may never be available to the general community, including those laboratories employing larger multi-gene or phylogenomic analyses. Furthermore, in many cases, for a variety of reasons (permits, accessibility, rarity of species, etc.) samples of many taxa are extremely difficult to obtain, thus limiting the scope of any phylogenetic, biogeographic and/or evolutionary analyses. Anything that can be done to BioBank biodiversity should be fully supported and, interestingly enough, any studies based on only one or a few genes can go a long way towards this being accomplished. Critically, from a biodiversity, evolutionary, and systematic perspective, studies using one or a few genes must be allowed to continue and must receive funding because they do provide invaluable information and resources towards biological inventories and expanding our understanding of intraspecific, specific, and supraspecific relationships. Globally, many laboratories can only generate single gene phylogenies, usually mtDNA and/or ctDNA genes, due to various constraints involving, for example, success in amplification and sequencing of additional genes and sequencing more difficult nDNA genes as well as financial constraints. However, these studies do provide three fundamental elements to the global biodiversity community that may otherwise never be obtained. These include 1) voucher museum specimens to document species existence in space and time; 2) at least some molecular data for taxa to be used in various types of analyses, and 3) BioBanked tissues. Thus, this increases the likelihood that taxa that may never be sampled would be available to the community. One must also remember that any phylogenies or analyses based on currently preferred much larger sample sizes of genes, are only hypotheses to be tested; so too are those based only on one or a few of genes. The funding, existence, and publication of these latter studies, however, provide valuable data/samples for any future studies. Studies using one or only a few genes provide valuable resources not only with sequence data for inclusion in future studies with more data, but equally, if not more important, tissues and specimens of often "impossible to difficult to obtain" taxa. Through global collaboration amongst scientists and/or laboratories publishing these types of smaller analyses of critically important samples can be used

for additional gene or genomic analyses that would never otherwise be possible.

Supporting Materials

Figure S1. Maximum likelihood tree constructed using Cyt *b*-P (552bp) data set, sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) was added "PT2012" at the end of taxon name in order to differentiate the newly added sequences. Nodes with bootstrap lower than 50 were collapsed.

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood tree constructed using Cyt *b*-C (1140bp) data set, sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) was added "PT2012" at the end of taxon name in order to differentiate the newly added sequences. Nodes with bootstrap lower than 50 were collapsed.

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood tree constructed using Cyt *b*-P&16s-P (1080bp) data set, sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) was added "PT2012" at the end of taxon name in order to differentiate the newly added sequences. Nodes with bootstrap lower than 50 were collapsed.

Figure S4. Maximum likelihood tree constructed using Cyt *b*-C&16s-P (1700bp) data set, sequences from Pethiyagoda et al. (2012) was added "PT2012" at the end of taxon name in order to differentiate the newly added sequences. Nodes with bootstrap lower than 50 were collapsed.

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